

POWER DEMAND IN AN AUGMENTED REALITY HOLOGRAPHIC DISPLAY*

Przemysław SKUROWSKI¹, Dariusz MYSZOR², Marcin PASZKUTA¹
Tomasz A. MOROŃ³, Krzysztof A. CYRAN¹

¹ Department of Computer Graphics, Vision and Digital Systems,

² Department of Department of Algorithmics and Software,

³ Department of Cybernetics, Nanotechnology and Data Processing

Silesian University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland

Introduction

Augmented reality devices are a class of sophisticated modern appliances that combine a real scene with computer-generated contents [1]. The head-mounted holographic displays are the most advanced devices up to today. They combine a real scene image with 3D computer graphics that is adopted interactively to the viewer. The latter is quite a demanding task, since during the user's motion it requires performing SLAM (simultaneous location and mapping), orientation identification, and recalculation and visualization of the whole 3D scene from changing point of view (PoV) [2]. The necessary calculations require having notable computational capabilities enclosed within a small headset resembling glasses – that problem is usually resolved with specialized hardware such as dedicated coprocessors, which perform computations efficiently.

The challenges towards energy consumption come from the fact that quite intensive computations are performed by the device, which is battery powered and worn onto head. Therefore, the usability can be limited by a frequent battery recharging and heat dissipated towards user head, which can degrade user's comfort [3] very quickly. The carbon footprint is of lesser importance for the case, since the devices of this class are still not very common nowadays and are battery powered, so they are not power greedy by design.

The Experiment and Results

Fig. 2. Test AR device

In this paper, we report the tests performed to evaluate the power consumed by the HL2 while displaying a scene with relatively simple, controlled content. The scene comprises static cubes without texture. The objects are located in the scene in flight simulator, between 2 and 4 meters from the observer. The HL2 was mounted on a dummy head, and it was connected to the sufficient [4] power supply through the custom built energy meter, which measures the instantaneous values of voltage, current and energy 5 times per second.

The research protocol involved iterative scene displaying (Fig. 2) of 0, 1, 5, 10, 100, and 500 cubes. During each iteration the scene was displayed for 120 seconds. For each configuration of cubes, there were two scenarios: a) the HL2 was static so the energy consumption by other sinks than visualization subsystem was minimized, b) the HL2 was on the move (horizontal rotation) so the influence of HL2 positioning subsystem on the power consumed by the device was analyzed. The averaged values of power consumed were reported for every scenario. Furthermore, energy demand by an idle device was measured, so the simple difference allowed us to estimate energy consumed for the visualization with respect to the scene complexity.

The average measured values of energy consumption are shown in Fig. 3, the values are accompanied with bars indicating standard deviation in measured power. The bars demonstrate how the energy demand grows with increasing scene complexity. At the same time introduction of the HL2 rotation slightly increases power consumption. Influence of this mechanism on power consumption seems to be also related to the number of objects located on the scene. Yet, due to hardware assistance by specialized coprocessor, the motion causes relatively small gain in power demand of the device. The notable change in power consumption (above 1W) can be noted between idle device and empty scene, where a test application is running but still displaying nothing. Another change (100mW) can be noted between empty scene and single cube displaying, which could be attributed to the initialization of 3D graphics by an application.

Fig. 2. Test scene with 500 cubes rendered

The error bars in the Fig. 3 indicate variability (standard deviation value) in consumed energy. They are on par for every considered case, regardless the complexity of the scene, which suggests it doesn't matter for the momentary variability to the drawn power. Just a bit smaller values are measured for empty scene and idle device.

Fig. 3. Power consumption during the visualization of the test scene for its variable complexity

Summary

The work covers the topic of energy efficiency of holographic application running on the state-of-the-art device in very generic test scenario – displaying of a static scene. We confirmed increasing power demand with increasing scene complexity. However, the energy drawn scales non-linearly, and certain contribution to the energy demand comes just from a running application (difference between idle and empty scene) and due to setting up whole visualization software infrastructure (scene, cameras) which could be identified as difference between empty scene and a single cube.

References

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